

POST-PRIMARY TEACHERS' MOTIVATIONS FOR FLIPPING, AND CONTINUING TO FLIP, THE MATHEMATICS CLASSROOM

Caoimhe McDonnell and Maria Meehan

School of Mathematics and Statistics, University College Dublin

The “flipped classroom” model is being implemented in educational settings internationally. In this model, the in-class and out-of-class activities of the traditional classroom are “flipped” – students might watch videos out of class, and work on tasks in class. Despite its popularity, research is mainly focused at higher education, and little is done in the Irish context. In this study, through one-to-one interviews with six post-primary teachers who have flipped their mathematics classrooms, we explore their initial motivations for doing so, and examine what motivates them to continue or discontinue the practice. Anticipated benefits, external factors, and being inspired by another, were given as motivations for initially flipping, while an improved classroom culture and perceived pedagogical benefits were reasons given for continuing the practice. Lack of time was a factor in teachers’ decisions to discontinue. For the four who continue to “flip”, their practice has evolved in a number of ways: a transition from using others’ videos to making one’s own; a decrease in frequency of flipping; and, an increase in the use of active learning in class. The teachers express a desire to belong to community of flipped classroom practitioners, in order to share experiences and resources, particularly mathematical tasks.

INTRODUCTION

The book by high-school science teachers Bergman and Sams (2012) has done a great deal to promote the methodology of “flipping the classroom” internationally. The authors were first motivated to create videos to enable students who missed class, to catch-up, and then realised that they could ask students to watch the videos at home, and use the in-class time to support students while they worked on problems. In essence, they flipped the order in which these activities are traditionally done. They describe how, over time, the flipped classroom evolved to the “flipped mastery classroom” (p. 51) where students work at their own pace, and demonstrate mastery of learning outcomes in their own time. Similarly, the much-viewed video of Salman Khan (2011) describes how, what started out as uploading mathematics videos for his cousins to watch remotely on YouTube, lead to the development of Khan Academy, which aims to use technology to remove the “one-size-fits-all lecture” (6:17) from the classroom. Both can be credited with popularising the idea of the flipped classroom.

In terms of research on flipped classrooms, Akçayir and Akçayir (2018) carried out a review of existing research from 2000 to 2016. They noted that 79% of the studies included were published in 2015-2016, with the increasing availability of technology suggested as a reason for the recent increase. Interestingly they found that most of the existing research was conducted at higher education, with only 16% of the 71 studies focusing on the primary and post-primary levels. In addition, much of the research focuses on the advantages and disadvantages of flipping the classroom, along with the nature of the in-class and out-of-class activities used. Given the current lack of research that examines the flipping of mathematics classrooms in Ireland, we are interested in exploring post-primary mathematics teachers’

experiences of flipping the classroom in Ireland. In this paper we narrow the focus to specifically address the following research questions (RQ):

RQ1. What initially motivates teachers to flip their mathematics classroom within the Irish post-primary system?

RQ2. What motivates these teachers to continue/discontinue to flip their mathematics classrooms, and for those who continue, how does their practice evolve over time?

LITERATURE REVIEW

One feature of using the flipped classroom model is that more in-class time is available for activities. Akçayir and Akçayir (2018) identified the following learning activities as the most common in flipped classrooms: discussion; small group activities; feedback to students; and, engaging students in problem-solving activities. Other activities carried out by students during in-class time include working on questions that would typically be completed as traditional homework, and engaging in active learning, such as peer instruction/interaction (Abeysekera & Dawson, 2015). During the in-class component, the teacher may act as a facilitator or tutor (Akçayir & Akçayir, 2018; Bergmann & Sams, 2012). The use of technology is a prominent feature of many flipped classrooms. The review by Akçayir and Akçayir (2018) found that videos were used in the out-of-class setting in 78.87% of flipped classroom, with the next most common uses comprising readings, quizzes and online discussion. Students may also be required to engage in note-taking while watching videos (Bergmann & Sams, 2012; de Araujo, Otten, & Birisci, 2017). The instructor must choose between using videos available online or making videos of their own. Bergmann and Sams (2012) recognise that it may be easier in the beginning to use videos made by others.

The most common advantages of the flipped classroom model that appear in the literature are the following: increased learner performance; flexible learning; improved student satisfaction and engagement; and, positive student feedback and perceptions (Akçayir & Akçayir, 2018). Interestingly, several studies have found that the flipped model benefits lower-performing students the most (Bhagat, Chang & Chang, 2016; Day, 2018; Ryan & Reid, 2016). Ryan and Reid (2016) found no difference in student performance when analysing the class as a whole. However, by splitting the students into groups using their pre-test scores, they found an increase in the performance of students belonging to the lowest third. Similarly, Day (2018) found that students in the lower two quartiles improved their grades when learning using the flipped model. The flexibility of the model allows students to work at their own pace and those who miss lessons can catch up more easily (Bergmann & Sams, 2012).

The most common disadvantages of the flipped classroom are the following: the time investment for the teacher; inadequate student preparation out-of-class; poor video quality; and, time investment out of class for the student (Akçayir & Akçayir, 2018). Other disadvantages of the model include the need for the teacher to engage in pre-class preparation in order for the in-class session to run as intended (Akçayir & Akçayir, 2018; de Araujo et al., 2017), and the need for the teacher to monitor student engagement in the out-of-class activities. Placing the responsibility on the students to do this work can make ensuring that they watch videos difficult (Bergmann & Sams, 2012; de Araujo et al., 2017).

A study similar to the one reported in this paper was conducted by de Araujo et al. (2017) at the high-school and pre-college level in the United States. They present two case studies of mathematics teachers who flipped their classrooms, examining their motivations for doing so, and their experiences with the flipped model. They found that both teachers were motivated to flip after hearing about the perceived advantages of the flipped model, in particular its potential to increase student-teacher interactions and deepen student understanding.

METHODOLOGY

One-to-one semi-structured interviews were conducted with seven post-primary mathematics teachers who had experience of flipping the classroom. Participants were sought via Twitter, a “Flipped Classroom Newsletter” (www.practicewhatyouteach.ie/flipped-newsletter), and through suggestions made by family, friends, and colleagues. Teachers were contacted via email and those who agreed to participate were interviewed during February and March 2019.

The interviews varied in length from 24 minutes to 1 hour and 31 minutes. One of the seven teachers had a misconception of the flipped model and therefore this interview was not included in the analysis. The other six interviews were transcribed and coded using thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006), taking an inductive approach. The six phases of thematic analysis as outlined in Braun and Clarke (2006, p. 87) were followed. Firstly, all six interviews were listened to repeatedly and read through. Secondly, initial codes were generated for two of the interviews. Thirdly, these codes were collated into themes. The remaining four interviews were then coded using the initial codes, and additional codes were added when required. In the fourth phase, thematic maps were generated, and in the fifth phase themes were named and described. Reporting the findings represents the sixth phase.

**Table 1: Information on participating teachers. *H = Higher Level, O = Ordinary Level, M = Mixed Level
Infrequent Flipping

Teacher (pseudonyms)	Time spent teaching maths	Time spent flipping	Level of year groups where class flipped*						School Gender	Currently flips
			1	2	3	4	5	6		
Alice	37 years	1.3 years	M			M	H		Mixed	Yes
Conor	8 years	2 months	M						All-boys	No
Frank	8 years	1.5 months	M	O	H		H	H	Mixed	No
John	15 years	5-6 years	M	H	H				Mixed	Yes
Karl	20 years	6-7 years**	M	H	H	M			Mixed	Yes
Rachel	3 years	1 year		M					Mixed	Yes

The six teachers’ experiences with flipping their classrooms varied considerably (see Table 1.) Alice, John, Karl, and Rachel currently engage in it, while Conor and Frank do not, and only engaged in it for a few months when they did. Alice trialled flipping two years ago for several months and then reverted to a non-flipped classroom. However, this year she is

flipping her fifth-year class consistently, and her first- and fourth-year classes, regularly. John has the most experience and has been implementing a flipped mathematics classroom for five to six years. However, his experience is limited to junior year groups as he has not taught senior classes during that time. Karl has used the flipped model infrequently since implementing it for approximately three months, six to seven years ago. Rachel flipped the classroom last year consistently. She is on leave this year but plans to reimplement the model when she returns to teaching. All six teachers work in public schools in the greater Dublin area, one of which is a Delivering Equality of Opportunity in Schools (DEIS) school.

FINDINGS

We first present the teachers' motivations for initially engaging in the flipped classroom, followed by their reasons for continuing/discontinuing the practice. We then examine how their practice has evolved over time.

Teachers' initial motivations to flip the mathematics classroom

Three main themes were identified in relation to what initially motivated our teachers to flip their mathematics classrooms. These are anticipated benefits, external factors and being inspired by others who had engaged in the practice.

Teachers spoke about the anticipated benefits of implementing a flipped classroom, which fall into three categories: use of out-of-class time; use of in-class time; and, the development of students. All six teachers assigned videos for students to view out-of-class, and the flexibility this provided to students was noted as a factor in the decision to flip. The teachers felt that videos would allow students to work at their own pace - they could pause, rewind and re-watch videos as needed. Karl noted: "I would always joke with them: 'With this thing you have got total control. You can mute me, you can fast forward me, you can rewind, you can do whatever you want'". It was also thought that videos would provide flexibility for the teacher when students were absent and allow them to catch up: "I could do things like when students are absent, they could still engage with my lesson which they wouldn't be able to do in my old style of teaching" (John). Teachers commented that the videos could be used as a revision tool and felt there was potential for the teacher to build a bank of video resources over time. It was anticipated that the out-of-class tasks would be manageable for all students, in contrast to the frustration they expressed with students not completing homework in the non-flipped model. As Alice commented:

I would say: "Why didn't you ask me in the class?" "I thought I understood it at the time but when I got home I didn't." I definitely felt it was the whole thing of getting past the place where students were coming in without their homework done.

The teachers anticipated that the extra in-class time, created by having students watch videos at home, would enable them to support students while working on questions: "The main advantage I hoped would be that I would be more available to the students to help them with their daily problems" (Rachel). They also felt it would allow students to spend more time doing mathematics: "Well I liked the idea of having more time in class to spend on problems" (Conor). Finally, the teachers hoped that flipping the classroom would enable them to foster the development of certain student attributes. They expected student attitude and enjoyment to

improve, as well as their sense of ownership of mathematics, and it was hoped that flipping could assist in the development of students as independent learners.

External factors that prompted the teachers to flip the classroom include: feeling under time pressure; meeting an expectation of varying one's teaching methodologies and effectively incorporating technology in the classroom; and, in one instance, an unplanned absence of the teacher. Rachel noted: "There is a bit of a push to encourage teachers to change their methodologies". In terms of being inspired by others who had engaged in the practice, the teachers heard of the flipped model from several sources, including YouTube videos, Initial Teacher Education, and Bergmann and Sams' (2012) book. Several teachers mentioned hearing Niall O'Connor (a mathematics teacher and flipped model advocate in Dublin) speak about his practice and Sal Khan's TED Talk (2011) as their inspirations for flipping.

Teachers' motivations for continuing/discontinuing the practice

Two themes were identified when analysing the reasons that the four teachers in our study, who continue to flip their mathematics classrooms, gave: classroom culture, and pedagogical benefits. In terms of classroom culture, a relaxed in-class setting, and more teacher enjoyment was cited as a motivation to continue to flip: "I certainly enjoy it much more, I interact more with the kids ... The kids now that I teach who are using the flipped classroom seem more relaxed in the classroom" (Alice). A perceived improvement in student attitude and enjoyment was also a motivation. Rachel noted that "Everybody was in much better form. The students were much more willing to engage ... I think students were more willing to do the problem-solving work in class". Most of the teachers spoke about receiving positive parental feedback. Karl continues to flip as he aims to use a variety of methodologies, including the flipped model, to engage students and improve their attitude and enjoyment.

Perceived pedagogical benefits motivate the teachers to continue flipping the classroom. They feel the model encourages students to become independent learners and hope it will better prepare students for life after school: "Students need to be independent learners. They need to [remove] the teacher as a crutch and be able to go into college and work on their own" (John). They believe that it helps students to develop valuable skills, as Rachel noted: "It encourages students to be a bit more autonomous and to take responsibility for their own learning, which in turn leads to development of skills" (Rachel). They feel that aspects of the flipped classroom help to foster independent learning in students, for example, placing more responsibility for learning from the videos onto the students.

The "extra" in-class time as a result of having students watch videos outside class is another reason to continue flipping. All four teachers feel that this time allows them to have a better awareness of student understanding: "I am spending time with them and there is a lot of like verbal questioning and so I would be learning a lot more about where they are at" (John). Karl observed that "you can see that they need help because you are just circling all the time".

Alice emphasised the importance of this:

We are probing a little or chatting a little or asking them "Why did you do that?" or whatever, it's amazing the lack of understanding ... you realise that students can get to a very high level in maths and not really understand some stuff.

Finally, two teachers referred to the potential of the flipped classroom to help with differentiation and personalisation. Alice utilises the flipped model to differentiate in one of her classes, with students of different abilities watching different videos and working on different problems. It is important to note that many of the teachers, during in-class sessions, do not expect all students to reach the same level or question and accommodate their varying abilities and pace. John's focus is on personalisation which he recognises as "learner led" and the "holy grail of education". He acknowledges that personalisation is an idealised vision that is yet to be fully achieved and he is committed to working towards it: "It's kind of big picture thinking but personalisation is, for me, what it is all about".

Time was the main factor that affected the two teachers' decisions to discontinue flipping the classroom. Frank feels that he lacks the time to create the videos, although he acknowledges that he would like to use the model again. Conor feels the time he had to invest into sourcing videos online is better spent "writing appropriate problems and finding good resources".

Evolution of teachers' practice

With regards to the evolution of the four teachers' practices of flipping, our findings include: a transition from using others' videos to making one's own videos; an increase in confidence in making videos; improved video quality; a decrease in frequency of flipping; and, an increase in the use of active learning and problem-solving strategies.

Interestingly, all four teachers who continue to flip now make their own videos. They have become less focused on making the perfect video: "This is not a YouTube production. This is just a classroom" (Alice), and are less self-conscious about uploading their videos onto YouTube. They feel that their videos have improved in quality and they are better at excluding irrelevant material resulting in shorter versions. Half of teachers also upgraded their equipment over time. For Karl and John, the frequency of their flipping has changed. John remarked: "When I first started flipping, I thought I had to be doing it five days a week, but I felt like I was missing out on other things as well". He now flips his classroom three days a week, using the other two days to implement other strategies. Similarly, Karl likes to use a variety of methodologies. Finally, how most of the teachers use the in-class time has changed, with some now investing more time in finding and creating mathematical tasks to encourage active learning, and promote problem-solving strategies.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The motivations of teachers to flip their classrooms initially, and their reasons for continuing to implement the model, largely mirror the advantages of the flipped classroom outlined in the literature (Akçayir & Akçayir, 2018). Time was cited by Conor and Frank as their reason for discontinuing the practice, and the time investment required to implement the model, especially initially, is evident in the literature (Akçayir & Akçayir, 2018). The teachers in both de Araujo et al's (2017) and this study who continue the practice of flipping feel that the benefits of flipping outweigh the time requirements. Conor and Frank flipped for the least amount of time which may have resulted in them not experiencing such benefits. Their practice may not have sufficiently evolved, resulting in a less time-efficient flipping in

comparison to the others. For example, Frank would spend thirty minutes making one video, whereas John could do so in fifteen.

There are similarities between the teachers' motivations to flip initially, and then to continue the practice. These include: enabling students to become independent learners; improved student attitude and enjoyment; and, "extra" in-class time. An initial motivation to flip was the availability of teacher support to students, while they are working on problems in class. By supporting the students during class, teachers had a better awareness of student understanding which is one of the motivations for them to continue to flip the classroom. The ability to build a bank of videos was an anticipated benefit that motivated teachers to implement the model in the first instance. However, it appears that this may not be as useful or beneficial as expected. Alice, Rachel, and John felt that building a bank of videos was not optimal, and that videos should be made by the teacher to adapt them for their own students: "I have heard other people ... using other teachers' flipped videos but I don't see how that could work. I think flipped has to be tailor made for your classroom" (Rachel). They also felt videos could be improved by providing up-to-date context: "I can build in more context and I can talk about how Tottenham won last night ... whereas if it's from last year's video I can't mention that" (John).

Interestingly, the external factors that motivated teachers to flip the classroom initially were not reflected in the literature. These included the desire to effectively incorporate technology into the classroom and the need to vary one's teaching methodologies. Recent initiatives in the Irish Education System may have impacted teachers' awareness of such factors. For example, the Department of Education and Skills have published a digital strategy for schools (DES, 2015a) and schools have been receiving grants to incorporate technology, such as tablets or laptops, into teaching and learning practices. Therefore, teachers are keenly aware of the expectation to integrate technology, which in turn provides motivation for using the flipped model. John noted: "I went to a one-to-one iPad school. I was given a tablet and I had no textbooks ... I wanted to find a way that I could use the technology that could enhance what I do". Similarly, the recent Junior Cycle reform, which has more of a focus on the development of student skills than before, has challenged teachers to move away from traditional teaching methods (DES, 2015b).

Knowing another teacher who flips the classroom appears to be essential. It often contributes to the initial decision to flip and to the subsequent decision to continue the practice. When asked what supports or resources would be useful for teachers deciding to flip, being in contact with experienced practitioners was discussed. Alice and Karl felt that having someone to guide a teacher through the process and answer their questions would be highly beneficial. John recognised that having a community of practice would support a teacher about to flip:

Having a community practice does make it easier of course because you can say 'Have you tried this?' or 'Have you tried that?' or, you can share ideas and say: 'Oh have you tried this, this is really good'.

The teachers felt that sharing examples of a flipped classroom specifically in the Irish context was important:

If they were given examples of what a flipped classroom looks like in their educational setting and not some magical school in England or in the States where everything looks fantastic and the kids are wearing blazers ... it would work quite well. (Frank)

Providing opportunities for teachers to meet each other and share their experiences would contribute to the successful implementation of flipped classrooms. We therefore recommend the establishment of a flipped classroom community of practice.

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